

STRESS AT WORKPLACE AND ITS MANAGEMENT BY NEW DIMENSION

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Abstract:

To find the various causes of stress and their impacts. Common stress management Tips and the success rate that we follow today. The Yoga and meditation benefits and how that reduces the stress in life to live better. How yoga keeps the body and mind healthy. The new dimension of stress management in the long happy life. The Yoga and meditation has been followed from ancient time. But the awareness and people interest are more due to percentage of people suffer by stress in increasing rapidly.

Introduction:

Stress is the common for everyone life in the universe. Stress management is the method or approach to reduce the stress and its one of the hottest issues across the world at different age group. It is more visible in today industries due to the business growth and competition and various health related issues. The stress is not a component is basically take place if any task or action which the individual feels discomfort, incapable, fear, unhappy, more work load, noise, pollution, Tight deadline, high targets and some of corporate goals.

Example, if you are going first time to the any new place you would have not known the how the place looks like and how far it may take to reach the place.. In this case expectation creates a little stress which you may not notice clearly sometime. The distance you travel first

time feels more than the return journey even the same distance by kilometer. For some of them it is other way. Both onward and return journey has different feel to various people depends on the state of mind or thought.

The people who feel more distance during the on wards and feel less distance while return due to the expectation about the new place and unknown stuff would create a little stress even though if it is same km by distance. For the people who feel short distance on onward journey and feel long distance on their return journey due to Unhappy or health reason.

Some of the major causes that creates stress

- **Insufficient Sleeping:**

Having enough sleep without disturbance keep the body and mind healthy. Due to work cultures and different work time the general routine changes and sleep time go to irregular clock. Having sleep for short to long time both create various problem. Adequate sleep is good for the healthy life. By doing Yoga gives sound sleep do to the calm and health mind.

- **Unbalanced Diet :**

Proper nutrition, mineral and vitamins are very crucial for the healthy life. Imbalance diet and skipping food would create a stress to the body and mind which creates health issues

- Being unhappy in your job
- Heavy workload or too much responsibility
- Working long hours
- Working under unhealthy or dangerous conditions
- Job insecurity
- Harassment at work
- Improper work life balance

Stress Management Tips

- **Walking:**

Small walk in a park out from the noise pollution which helps better blood flow also brain get oxygen which will help to clear your mind from stress. Try to avoid any discussion while walking, better have a walk alone to free mind.

- **Deep Breaths:**

When you feel tension building, push back from your desk, close your eyes, visualize a “happy place” and take five to 10 deep, relaxing breaths to bring yourself back to a calm place and again focus your mind. This also works if you’re stuck in traffic — just keep your eyes on the road.

- **Exercise:**

Stretching body loosen the muscles and feel more relax and stress free due to the increase in blood flow throughout the body. Which will also help to cure some medical problem. Please consult professionals and learn the proper stretching exercise. This is mandatory for the every individual for the long stretch work hours, sitting in the same position for more hours.

- **Music:**

Basically music is best entertainment, apart from it help to reduce the stress. If you say music, there may type like pop, rock, classical, Hindustan and instrumental with theme and natural music. Calm music and instrumental which help to feel stress free.

- **Socialism:**

Interaction with various people and friendly chat with the best friend or loved one will help to reduce stress.

- **Keep Smiling:**

Smile Reduces the stress the drastically and keep calm and peaceful. Helps better relation with co-workers.

Major Impacts due to Stress

- **Bad Habits:**

Stress could push the person to choose the alternative action or habit to reduce the stress. Behavior such as smoking, drinking, drugs and substance abuse. These habits become addiction later in the long run which leads to major health issue which basically impacts the person personal life and career life.

- **Health :**

High or continuous stress levels affected the self-esteem of the employees. Prolonged exposure to stress without effective coping mechanisms either by individual or by the organization could lead to a physical and mental health issues. Most likely the depression, heart disease, multiple organ failure and Immune disorders etc.

- **Angry:**

Getting angry for everything and with everyone due to the various reasons, not enjoy the life and break in relationship and depression

Many researches has done and found the IT /ITES staffs are more stressed. Based on the survey there are various approaches methods has been implemented by some of the corporates. To reduce stress at workplace by providing outdoor trainings, consulting and mentoring and entertainment and fun activities at corporate to make the employee perform better with more satisfaction. Which is not consistent and not a permanent remedy for the reduce stress.

Yoga

Yoga is the physical, mental, and spiritual practices or disciplines which originated in ancient India with a view to attain a state of permanent peace. The term yoga can be derived from either of two roots, yogi yoga (to yoke) or yuj samādhau (to concentrate).

Yoga Benefits

- **Physical fitness** : Keep body fit and active without tiredness
- **Mental Fitness** : Remove mind blocks and help to be calm, rejuvenated and help to more confident
- **Psychological changes**: The behaviour aspects on dealing with people.
- **Intuitive**- Spontaneous action and response at work
- **Creativity** – Creativity will be high to the removed mind blocks. Thought flow is free

Figure 1: Stress from various sources

Survey has been conducted across the IT companies in Bangalore the survey response percentage was 63% and analysis performed based on 250 samples, as per the responses the Number participants responded stating that on Work creates more stress by 88 participants. , followed by commitment by 78 participants.

Figure 2: Most effective technique on stress management

As per the survey the most effective technique on stress management is Yoga and meditation

Conclusion

Stress management is most crucial for today's work life.. Stress management which also has linkages to the Time management, Knowledge management and anger management. In the fast growing world improper time management creates more stress which unable to finish the task in the given time or deadline set by the organization. Second due to lack of skill set to serve in the organization demands when required. Uncontrolled anger or negative behaviour at work place which create disturbed and unfriendly environment at work place. The Study concludes apart from following the simple practice like Walking, Deep Breathes, Exercise, Music and interaction the Yoga and Meditation given better result in the stress management in short term and long run. Consistent practice brings lot of maturity in the behavior which create peaceful and stress less life. Which intern increase the happy life with the health body and mind. The Study proves that Yoga and meditation reduce stress and create stress less life for well-being in permanentely. The Corporate should think about the initiate corporate level yoga program for the employee to reduce the stress level.

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